

TRAINING THE CONTENT AND FORM OF THE PROJECT ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *In this article, the inclusion of schoolchildren in the project activity is to form their self-esteem, to teach them to reflect and predict, as educational tools, the project activity is to allow the content and management of the project, to cite sample topics of projects from the subject "Mathematics", "ancient measurements", "Ratios around Uzbekistan", "some fast calculation techniques", "mathematics in human life", "spatial numbers" were considered.*

Keywords: *design, education, student, training sessions, quality result. activity.*

Project this special systemli time with limited, targeted, change results quality for set requirements with funds and resources spending and known a organizatio with you can the restrictions summary. Of the project features [1].

1. Complex and many dated task availability.
2. Events unique results.
3. Limited start of the work and the date of completion is determined.
4. Limited resources and budget.
5. The participation of numerous people, usually multiple functional the divisions of the organization.
6. The order of the tasks specified.
7. His attention to achieve the final goal.
8. As a result, to obtain a final product or to provide services.

Design-this is the main future activities of students and teachers in the development of the initial details.

The teacher create lessons the lessons of the project, project activities, lesson or a technological map of the lesson plan that create the technology to implement it the choice of those who submit to the students the purpose of the lessons which allow you to organize the activities of mechanisms. Readers of the activities of the project educational, cognitive, creative or playful activities that bring a problem to solve, provided a detailed description of its (project) form. This project is the basis of the method - readers knowledge, skills, ability development, build independently of their knowledge, information that the ability to act, space critical thinking development. Didaktika a particular topic from the area if the project method , when used in private methods will be. [4] The didactic method category. This technical package are mastering certain operations, practical or theoretical knowledge in the field of certain activities. To know this way of knowing, the process of organizing method. Therefore, if you are us project, we have to speak about the method of, or is configured in this manner, finished with a clear need to be applied the way to achieve the goal through the problem to develop more didactic (technology) we are referring to. The results of this see, understand and can be applied in real practice. To teach you how to achieve such results, you need the following: independent thinking in children the problem and find solutions, to attract, to do this in various areas of knowledge, the ability to forecast the possible consequences of different solutions and results, the ability to identify cause-

effects relationships. Always independent business is the focus of the project method. Method always includes the project to solve some problems. Solve the problem to make, on the one hand, include the use of a combination of teaching methods and tools and on the other hand the needs and various science, technology, and combine skills in the various fields of knowledge, technology, means the creative area. The results of the completed projects, as they say, "material" must be, that if there is a theoretical problem, then its exact solution can be applied to specific outcomes is ready for implementation. In fact, the project method individual or group, but if that method, then it implies a certain cognitive education and technics. Educational technology as if you are talking about the method of the project, then this technology, research, search, refers to the collection of the problematic methods. Their creative and in a nutshell.[2]

The introduction of the main tasks of the project method in mathematics lessons:

- use the obtained research experience individual show the skills of a student or group of students.

-- to realize interest to mathematics; increase your knowledge of mathematics, take out and delivery.

- demonstrate the level of mathematical cognition; increase their ability.

The contact form to participate in the team:

- education, development, social to the high level of sharpen.

Ta'lim and in the society requires the following changes:

school teachers from a new approach to the educational process.

In the conditions of modern life it is not enough to only have the knowledge, skills and abilities of you more and more, and you should take them them in real life, you should get used in a real situation. In today's rapidly evolving information society in any situation this knowledge is really not a lot of knowledge, but the ability ability to apply knowledge independently and to get them xakikiy is considered.

I asosiyari educational and cognitive activity in the form of this one-
young readers factors stimulating the development of education.

The project method-this is our new words that children often hear. The project method-the joint activities of teachers and students, this would be the solution of the problem, aims to find out the problematic situation. The second generation standards put the function of the formation of young students from powers: the decision to make them, teach them to be communicative, mobile the project activities to deal with it.

The project consists of the following activities:

- 1) analysis of problems;
- 2) goal setting;
- 3) choosing the means to achieve it;
- 4) information search and processing, analysis and synthesize it;
- 5) evaluate results and conclusions.

The purpose of the activity by the students project topics (on the basis of integration) the obtained knowledge, skills and learning ability during different taken. Principles of organization of the project activity:

- 1) you should be able to implement the project;
- 2) create the conditions necessary for the successful implementation of projects, that is, the teacher must prepare the students for the implementation of projects;

3) teachers provide project management-discussion
the chosen topic, the work plan;

4) on the project individual their work ensures that each student's pace of development to reach her level.

To solve the problem of mutual dependence and the practical implementation of the results of the project to consider it for the education system or method very attractive. Training is very specific to the requirements of the project. Requirements of them are usually simple and most importantly "the children comes from." All can and should be the subject for students to grasp. How the child is small, so the project is simple. The activities of the project the choice of the shape of the product important organizational task. The results of the project's activities, which can be read in this thread, here is a list of quotes.[3]

1) the game table;

2) business plan;

3) video;

4) exhibition;

5) newspaper;

6) journal;

7) Bill;

8) the feast of the article;

9) scenario;

10) study guide.

For example, the presentation of the project can be of different types.

1. Scientific report.

2. Ekspeditsiya research report.

3. Press conference.

4. Travel.

5. Advertising.

Students design-the process of working on this educational project, the particular "product" in the form of process to achieve the intended results. The project is directed to the following method:

1) development of critical thinking;

2) development of creative thinking;

3) ability to work with information;

4) ability to work in team;

5) know the culture of communication.

The organization is becoming a popular form of design students. The level of creative activity of students in various educational institutions. Did not find evidence in favor of applying it and many different teachers. So, school pupils add them to the activities of the project self-esteem teaches you to shape and reflect and predict. As educational tools, the project allows you to manage both the content of the project activities. The end of the article I "mathematics" project has been causing the issues typical of the subject. "the ancient of measure", "Uzbekistan, the surrounding ratios", "some quick calculation technique", "mathematics in the life of man", "the number of spatial" and others.

REFERENCES

1. Muslimov N. A., Usmonboeva H. M. "Innovative learning technologies and pedagogical kompetentlik" educational and methodical complex on the module. – Tashkent: TDP, 2016. 238-b.
2. Muslimov N. A., Rakhimov Z. T., Hodjaev A. A., Yusupov B. E. "Education technologies. Training guide." – Tashkent: "Arrival" publishing house, 2020. 192 b.
3. Ochilov M. "New pedagogical technologies." – Against: "Nasaf", 2000. B 75.
4. Rakhimov T. Z. "Kompetentlik the development of Education in the process of training students to know." // "Modern education" scientific-popular magazine practical, 2020, №3 (88).